

NEWSLETTER

Advancing AI & Data Engineering to drive industrial innovation

The PANDORA project focuses on advancing AI and data engineering to drive industrial innovation and enhance the EU economy. It addresses challenges in IoT-generated data processing, aiming to create a single data market for Europe's global competitiveness. PANDORA aims to develop AI-driven frameworks for preparing and delivering trustworthy datasets, enhancing AI models' accuracy and sustainability in AIoT systems. Its mission includes increasing autonomy, trustworthiness, and energy efficiency in managing IoT datasets for smarter and more responsive devices in smart space ecosystems.

Objectives

- Advance research excellence in the development of resilient, transparent, and human-centered AI approaches towards optimized and autonomous data processing and use.
- Provide novel methods, mechanisms, and tools for the development of customizable, and trustworthy datasets for model-based AI developments.
- Support the development and the continual autonomous operations of robust and energy efficient "data in AI" pipelines across the computing continuum.
- Provide a cross-sector and multi-variant smart data space to realize the PANDORA framework and validate the data-enabled trustworthy AI mechanisms in real life scenarios.
- Foster synergetic approaches in the EU industrial and scientific research communities and promote international collaboration on efficient and trustworthy AI approaches.
- Enhance the EU multidisciplinary competencies in the fields of industrial AI, data and robotics and embrace open innovation.

Pilots

SIEMENS AKTIENGESELLSCHAFT
Distributed AI for predictive edge "apps" re-allocation in production cells

ERICSSON AB
5G-enabled smart building for semantically enhanced AI training (EAB ERICSSON)

PHILIPS CONSUMER LIFESTYLE BV
AI-driven autonomous vision systems for inspecting manufactured goods

FRAMATOME GMBH
AI driven increase of safety in critical hydrogen infrastructure

ELVALHALCOR
Enhanced AIoT sensing infrastructures to promote energy efficiency in critical manufacturing processes

Key Facts

Title: A Comprehensive Framework enabling the Delivery of Trustworthy Datasets for Efficient AIoT Operation
Acronym: PANDORA
GA No: 101135775
Start: 01 April 2024
End: 31 March 2027
Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2023-HUMAN-01-01
Type of action: HORIZON-RIA

Consortium

The PANDORA consortium brings together 25 organisations from 14 different EU Members States and Associated countries, that bear strong interest and relevance to the project objectives and are highly committed in the delivery of scientific excellence and deployment of breakthrough technologies in the fields of trustworthy, efficient extreme data handling and novel green AI applications.

News

June 10, 2024
Multimodal Adaptation of Unimodal Deep Learning models
In this paper, AARHUS University in collaboration with Tampere University of Applied Sciences address the main challenges associated with the task of multimodal Dynamic Facial Expression Recognition performance, which they...

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April 23, 2024
PANDORA Project Kick-Off Meeting
PANDORA Horizon Europe project kick-off meeting in #Brussels, hosted by #NTUA and #AEGIS, and attended by our PO Riku Leppänen. First day focused on the overall #PANDORA solution and the...

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Message from the Project Coordinator

The PANDORA project was launched on April 1, 2024 and brings together 25 partners from 14 EU member states, Canada, and India. Its mission is to address the critical challenges of data availability, data trustworthiness, and energy efficiency in Artificial Intelligence of Things (AIoT) systems. These challenges are central to developing and advancing "data for AI" pipelines within AIoT ecosystems. A multidisciplinary team of experts from various scientific and industrial fields is collaborating to create a comprehensive suite of mechanisms, technologies, and tools for the PANDORA AI-based, domain-informed framework. This framework will be applied and validated through real-life trial cases, addressing the digital strategy and operational needs of five key industry sectors in Europe. The overarching goal is to enhance the EU's global competitiveness in industrial AIoT systems. Stay tuned for further developments and updates!

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